

Reducing the climate change impacts of lithium-ion batteries by their cautious management through integration of stress factors and life cycle assessment

Samppa Jenu^{a,*}, Ivan Deviatkin^{a,b}, Ari Hentunen^a, Marja Myllysilta^a, Saara Viik^a, Mikko Pihlatie^a

^a VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd., P.O. Box 1000, FI-02044 VTT, Finland

^b Lappeenranta-Lahti University of Technology LUT, P.O. Box 20, FI-53851, Lappeenranta, Finland

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Li-ion battery
Degradation stress factors
Cycle life model
Climate change
Carbon handprint
Carbon footprint

ABSTRACT

The use of Li-ion batteries for stationary energy storage in households represents a viable solution to mitigate climate change when compared with the reference situation of electricity supply from the grid in various countries. This study quantifies the climate change impacts of production, use, and disposal of NMC batteries and compares the impacts with provision of electricity from grids of six European countries to calculate their carbon handprints, a measure of positive climate impacts. The study also develops a general cycle life model for NMC batteries to show the impact of various stress factors on the lifetime of the battery, which was then used to show the impact of battery management on its climate change impacts due to varying energy throughput. Of the countries studied, the carbon handprint was the highest in Bulgaria at 13,450 kg CO₂-eq. per energy throughput of the battery during its life cycle of 25.3 MWh. The lowest handprint achieved was in Finland at 2000 kg CO₂-eq., while no handprint was achieved in Norway. Uncertainty in the data on Li-ion battery production and recycling was found to be of minor importance when the entire life cycle of the batteries was studied and compared with the baseline scenario. Operating temperature, cycle depth and average state of charge during cycling have significant impact on the lifetime of Li-ion batteries and hence on their carbon handprint. The longest lifetime with NMC batteries can be achieved by cycling the battery at low cycle depth at an average state of charge of around 50% and an operating temperature close to 25 °C. Operating the battery at 50% cycle depth instead of 90% cycle depth more than doubled the carbon handprint in all the countries studied except Norway.

1. Introduction

The demand for effective measures to combat climate change has strengthened as the understanding of climate change and its devastating consequences has increased in society. Of the multiple measures proposed to prevent global warming, the generation of electricity from renewable sources is considered among the most prominent [1]. Citizens and municipalities are getting involved in such actions through the installation of local renewable energy facilities, such as solar panels or wind turbines. Wide generation and utilization of renewable energy from solar and wind is strongly restricted by the intermittence of such energy sources, among other factors [2]. A consistent and reliable supply of electricity from solar and wind could partly be ensured through the application of distributed energy storage systems based on batteries. Various batteries including Li-ion batteries (LIBs) among others can be coupled with photovoltaics (PV) at the level of communal

grids to form PV-battery stationary systems [3]. Opiyo [3] finds that LIBs have the fastest charging/discharging cycles and highest efficiencies of up to 99% as compared to other batteries studied, yet the cost of LIBs is an inhibitory factor for their wider deployment.

Along with the relatively high cost of LIBs and the technological immaturity of LIBs in stationary applications, uncertainty and confusion regarding their environmental impacts are hindering their wider utilization on a global scale. The amount of primary data available on the environmental impacts of LIB production has increased in recent years, yet these data vary [4]. For example, Peters and Weil [5] emphasize parameters such as the energy demand for cell manufacture, the type of electrode binder used, and the battery management system inventory as greatly affecting the environmental impacts of LIB manufacture, while Ellingsen et al. [6] highlight the high importance of the type of electricity used in cell and battery manufacturing processes. The variations in the data on LIB manufacture could, however, be of little

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: samppa.jenu@vtt.fi (S. Jenu).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2019.101023>

Received 27 February 2019; Received in revised form 15 October 2019; Accepted 16 October 2019

Available online 12 November 2019

2352-152X/ © 2019 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

importance when the entire life cycle of LIBs is considered. The life cycle impacts of LIBs are expected to be strongly affected by the use phase of LIBs [7]. The use phase is important due to the substitution of electricity generated using grid mix technologies with electricity generated by PVs and stored in LIBs. Finally, the end-of-life of batteries, which also varies considerably, should be included and considered.

When considering the use phase of LIBs, the impact of degradation stress factors on the lifetimes of batteries should be analysed as this will affect the amount of electricity stored and delivered through LIBs. Several studies on the environmental impact of LIBs have highlighted the need for research on increasing the lifetime of LIBs [4,8,9]. The lifetime of LIBs could be prolonged by their cautious use and increased awareness among end users of the potential climate change impacts of how batteries are used. Previous research shows that operating temperature and the way the battery is cycled strongly affect the number of cycles LIBs can perform [10,11].

In the literature, there are various Li-ion battery ageing models, from the material level to battery pack level [12]. Cell-level models are typically based on extensive testing data and therefore provide accurate results, but are limited to a specific cell type and test conditions. Many of the ageing models presented in the literature require extensive information on the battery to be modelled. Often such information is not available, and the expected lifetime reported by the manufacturer is the only information available. Typically, battery manufacturers report the expected cycle life of the battery under specified operating conditions. In many cases, the environmental conditions and the way the battery is operated in the application differ significantly from the operating conditions reported by the manufacturer. In addition, the expected calendar life of the battery may be reported, but often with no knowledge of the actual operating conditions or practices. To be able to estimate the lifetime of the battery in a particular application, a lifetime model that takes into account different environmental conditions and operating practices is required. Such a lifetime model can then be utilized in the design of battery systems, in battery techno-economic evaluation or in battery life cycle assessment.

This study has several research objectives. First, the study systematically analyses the climate change impacts of manufacturing, using, and disposing of NMC Li-ion batteries. Nickel manganese cobalt oxide (NMC) was selected among various Li-ion battery chemistries for this study due to its good energy storage properties and its already significant and growing share in distributed energy storage systems along with other applications [13,14]. The analysis helps to better understand the climate change impacts LIBs across their entire life cycle, including the provision of electricity throughout their life cycle, and disposal. The use phase also includes the provision of solar panels for electricity generation. Secondly, the study compares the impact of the electricity provision through the system based on solar panels and LIBs with conventional electricity provision from grids in the context of six countries: Bulgaria, Germany, the Netherlands, Spain, Norway, and Finland. Such analysis helps to identify the impact of different carbon intensities on the break-even point. Thirdly, the study develops a general cycle life model for NMC batteries to show the impact of various stress factors on the lifetime of the batteries under various cycling conditions. The model was built upon existing cycle life data retrieved from scientific literature. Finally, the study combines the lifetime model with the results of climate change impact assessment to examine how different ways of using the batteries affect their climate change impact throughout their life cycle. This analysis helps to better understand the impact of different battery use patterns on their climate change impact through increased or reduced lifetime and thereby through lower or higher renewable energy throughput.

2. Overview of degradation stress factors

The degradation of Lithium-ion batteries is a complex combination of electrochemical and mechanical processes that lead to capacity

decrease and power fading [10,15,16]. Most of these processes cannot be studied independently as they occur simultaneously at similar timescales and interact with each other. The degradation processes mainly occur in the electrodes or in the electrolyte while interacting with the electrodes [15]. The degradation mechanisms at the electrodes are strongly dependent on the electrode composition and are different for anodes and cathodes [10]. The degradation is commonly divided into three degradation modes: loss of lithium inventory, loss of active anode material, and loss of active cathode material [16]. A key degradation mechanism related to the loss of lithium inventory is the formation of a solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) layer on the graphite anode. The SEI layer is naturally created during the first charge and protects the anode from corrosion and the electrolyte from reduction [10]. The SEI layer develops over time as the battery is operated, resulting in a continuous loss of lithium ions. From the application perspective, the degradation processes can be divided into two groups: degradation during active use (cycle ageing) and degradation during passive storage (calendar ageing) [10]. Cycle ageing includes all degradation processes that occur when the battery is charged or discharged. Calendar ageing refers to the irreversible loss of capacity and increase in internal resistance that occur during storage.

Environmental conditions and the way the battery is operated both affect the degradation rate and the impact of different degradation mechanisms [10,11]. In the literature, the factors affecting the degradation rate of a battery are called stress factors [11,17–19] or ageing factors [19,20]. In this study, degradation stress factors refer to all operating practices or conditions that accelerate degradation of the battery and thus shorten the lifetime of the cell, and can be divided according to the type of ageing: stress factors related to cycle ageing, and stress factors related to calendar ageing. In this study, experimental cycle life and calendar life test results from the literature were reviewed and analysed to identify the main degradation stress factors.

2.1. Calendar ageing stress factors

Two main stress factors related to calendar ageing were identified: environmental temperature and battery state of charge (SOC) during storage. High storage temperature facilitates secondary reactions, such as corrosion, and accelerates the loss of lithium, resulting in capacity fade [10]. Käbitz et al. [21], Richter et al. [22] and Schmitt et al. [23] observed a significant acceleration in capacity decline and resistance increase in NMC cells with increased storage temperature. Corresponding results have been detected with NMC-LMO cells [24] and LFP cells [25–27]. High SOC during storage results in higher battery degradation compared to lower SOC levels [10]. The results of the calendar life tests for NMC cells by Ecker et al. [28] and Käbitz et al. [21] show that calendar ageing is fast at high storage SOC levels and significantly slower at low SOC levels. Calendar life tests with NMC-LMO cells by Wu et al. [24] indicate a corresponding dependence on storage SOC, albeit with slightly smaller differences in calendar life. Similarly, the calendar life of LFP cells also changes as a function of storage SOC, although storage temperature is a clearly more significant factor [25–27].

2.2. Cycle ageing stress factors

The main identified cycle ageing stress factors are cycle depth, average SOC of the cycles, temperature during cycling, and the magnitude of charge and discharge current. In this study, the term cycle depth (Δ DOD, equal to Δ SOC) is used to describe the depth of the discharge-charge cycle regardless of the initial SOC. Cycling the battery at high cycle depth accelerates the degradation processes in the cell and thus decreases its lifetime [10]. Experimental results by Ecker et al. [28] and de Hoog et al. [29] confirm that the cycle depth strongly affects the cycle life of NMC cells. The cycle life of the examined cells increases significantly when the cycle depth is reduced. Wang et al.

[30] have studied the effect of cycle depth on the cycle life of NMC-LMO cells and have found a similar dependency. Omar et al. [31] have obtained corresponding results for LFP batteries, whereas Sarasketa-Zabala et al. [32] observed that LFP cells cycled with both large and small cycle depth show the slowest degradation. Altogether, the majority of experimental results in the literature indicate that the cycle life increases as the cycle depth is decreased and, in many cases, an exponential relationship between cycle depth and cycle life is evident.

Experimental cycle life tests by Ecker et al. [28] indicate that the average SOC of the cycles has a significant effect on the cycle life of NMC batteries. Cycling at low or high average SOC seems to decrease the cycle life, whereas the longest cycle life was achieved with cycling at around 50% SOC. Similar results were obtained with cycle depths from 5% to 50% [28]. Surprisingly, not many experimental studies related to the effect of average SOC on cycle life were found from the literature. Jiang et al. [33] studied the cycle life of LFP batteries cycled at different average SOCs. The batteries cycled at around mid-level SOC had the lowest capacity fade, while the battery cycled at low average SOC showed increased capacity fade and the battery cycled at high average SOC suffered the fastest capacity fade [33].

Cell temperature during cycling is one of the key degradation stress factors related to cycle ageing. Both elevated temperature and low temperature during cycling accelerate the degradation processes in the cell [15]. Cycling Li-ion batteries at very low temperatures can lead to lithium plating and lithium dendrite growth [15,34]. Experimental cycle life tests by Käbitz et al. [21], Jalkanen et al. [35] and Richter et al. [22] reveal that the cycle life of NMC batteries decreases as the temperature is increased from room temperature to 55–65 °C. No studies with data on NMC cells cycled in temperatures below room temperature were found during this work. Wang et al. [30] have studied the cycle life of NMC-LMO batteries at temperatures from 10 °C to 46 °C and observed that both low and high temperatures trigger more capacity fade compared to mid-range temperatures. Omar et al. [31] observed that at 0 °C the cycle life of LFP cells is lower than at room temperature and at –18 °C the cycle life dropped dramatically [31]. As with other Li-ion battery types, the cycle life of LFP batteries decreases in temperatures above room temperature [31,36].

Another stress factor affecting the cycle life of Li-ion batteries is the magnitude of charge and discharge currents. The cycle life of NMC batteries decreases as the charging or discharging rate is increased [22,37]. Experimental results by Schuster et al. [37] indicate that increasing the charging rate from 0.2C or 0.5C to 1C already accelerates ageing. Keil et al. [38] observed that high charging current accelerated the degradation rate of an LMO-NMC cell and LFP cell, whereas high charging current had no negative effect on the examined NMC-LCO cell [38]. Wang et al. [30] observed that the cycle life of NMC-LMO batteries decreases as the discharge rate is increased from 2C to 6.5C. Omar et al. [31] observed that both increased charging and discharging rate decrease the cycle life of LFP cells, but with charging rate the decrease is faster. The reduction in cycle life is closely related to the heating of the cells due to high current rates [31].

3. Methodology

This section describes the type of LIB studied, the methodology for assessing the climate impact of the LIB and its use in a stationary application to substitute electricity from the grid, and the methodology for developing a general cycle life model for the NMC battery studied.

3.1. Studied Li-ion battery

In this study, a LIB with nickel manganese cobalt oxide (NMC) cathode and a graphite anode was studied. Table 1 lists the parameters of the battery studied as reported by the manufacturer. The warranty condition of the battery studied was 313,000 Ah and the storage capacity 111.4 Ah. Therefore, the expected cycle life of the battery in the

Table 1
Parameters of the studied NMC battery.

Battery parameter	Value
Cell chemistry	NMC
Nominal capacity	10 kWh
Ah per pack	111.4 Ah
Warranty (daily, 90% DOD, 1C)	313 000 Ah
Max charge/discharge current	132 A
MAX C-rate	1.2 C
MAX DOD nominal	90%
Initial SOH	100%
Roundtrip efficiency	90%
Expected calendar life	10 years

reference conditions was 2810 full cycle equivalents (FCEs). Daily cycling, a cycle depth (Δ DOD) of 90% and a C-rate of 1C were mentioned in the warranty conditions. An average state of charge (SOC) of 50% and room temperature (25 °C) were assumed to represent the reference conditions of use of the battery since these parameters were not specified by the battery manufacturer. Under the reference daily cycling condition of 1 FCE per day, the battery would reach end-of-life after 7.7 years. This service life calculated from the warranty is slightly shorter than the expected calendar life specified by the manufacturer, which is 10 years. As the battery cycling conditions for expected calendar life of 10 years were not specified, the warranty-based service life of 7.7 years in known cycling conditions was used in this study. During its service life, the energy throughput of the battery would be 25.3 MWh accounting for a roundtrip efficiency of 90% and nominal capacity of 10 kWh.

A cycle life of 2810 FCEs in the reference conditions (cycle depth of 90%, average SOC of 50%, operating temperature of 25 °C) was used as a reference for the cycle life model. The reference conditions, expected service life (7.7 years) and the energy throughput under the reference conditions (25.3 MWh) were used to calculate the carbon footprint of the LIB in the baseline scenario before implementation of the battery lifetime model.

3.2. Li-ion battery cycle life model

The cycle life model developed in this study is based on experimental cycle life test results collected from the literature. In this study, the model is developed for NMC chemistry, but the same modelling method could be applied also for other Li-ion battery chemistries. To study the effect of each degradation stress factor separately, results from cycle life tests where only one stress factor is varied while others remain constant were examined from the literature. When determining the cycle life of the battery from reported cycle life test results, 80% of the initial capacity (80% SOH) was considered to be the end of life criterion for the battery. If the battery was not cycled until 80% of its initial capacity, linear extrapolation using the first and the last data point was used. If the battery was cycled below 80% of the initial capacity, the number of cycles at 80% SOH was used as the cycle life. If the battery was cycled at lower than 100% cycle depth, the number of cycles cycled was converted into full cycle equivalents ($FCE = N_{\text{cycles}} \times \Delta$ DOD) to be able to compare the obtained cycle life results.

The most comprehensive cycle life test results available for NMC cells related to cycle depth, and average SOC and temperature stress factors were utilized to form stress factor models for each studied stress factor. The stress factor models describe the relationship between the investigated stress factor and cycle life of the battery. The stress factor models are presented in Section 4.1. The charge and discharge current stress factor was excluded due to the typically low C-rates used in stationary energy storage systems.

Based on the stress factor models, a cycle life model for NMC

chemistry was developed. The battery cycle life model estimates the cycle life of the battery taking into account the cycle depth, average SOC and cell temperature stress factors. Our inclusion of the stress factors in the model is similar to the approach used by Xu et al. [39]. The effect of each stress factor is considered separately in the model:

$$L_{ref}^{cyc} = S_{\Delta DOD}^{cyc}(\Delta DOD, \Delta DOD_{ref}) S_{SOC}^{cyc}(SOC, SOC_{ref}) S_T^{cyc}(T, T_{ref}) L_{ref}^{cyc} \quad (1)$$

where L_{ref}^{cyc} is a reference cycle life with reference cycle depth (ΔDOD_{ref}), average SOC (SOC_{ref}) and temperature (T_{ref}). Coefficients $S_{\Delta DOD}^{cyc}$, S_{SOC}^{cyc} and S_T^{cyc} describe the effects of each degradation stress factor on battery cycle life. The stress factor coefficients can be calculated using the stress factor models $f_{\Delta DOD}^{cyc}$, f_{SOC}^{cyc} and f_T^{cyc} :

$$S_{\Delta DOD}^{cyc}(\Delta DOD, \Delta DOD_{ref}) = \frac{f_{\Delta DOD}^{cyc}(\Delta DOD)}{f_{\Delta DOD}^{cyc}(\Delta DOD_{ref})} \quad (2)$$

$$S_{SOC}^{cyc}(SOC, SOC_{ref}) = \frac{f_{SOC}^{cyc}(SOC)}{f_{SOC}^{cyc}(SOC_{ref})} \quad (3)$$

$$S_T^{cyc}(T, T_{ref}) = \frac{f_T^{cyc}(T)}{f_T^{cyc}(T_{ref})} \quad (4)$$

3.3. Impact of NMC batteries on climate change

The present study follows the key principles of the international standards on life cycle assessment (LCA) SFS-EN ISO 14040 [40] and SFS-EN ISO 14044 [41]. A typical LCA study includes four stages: goal and scope definition, life cycle inventory (LCI), life cycle impact assessment (LCIA), and life cycle interpretation.

3.3.1. Goal and scope definition

The goal of this study was to quantify the climate change impacts of i) production of NMC batteries using the parameters specified in Section 3.1, ii) the use of NMC batteries for storage of electricity generated with PVs, and iii) NMC batteries disposal. Furthermore, the study compared the alternative scenario of NMC batteries use with the reference scenario of electricity supply from the grid. The two studied product systems are shown in Fig. 1. The function of the studied product systems was to supply electricity. The functional unit of the studied system was the amount of electricity delivered with one NMC battery as specified in Section 3.1, which was 25.3 MWh in the reference case. The amount of electricity delivered varied when the battery lifetime model was implemented, yet the equivalence of the studied scenarios and systems in terms of the electricity delivered was maintained.

Fig. 1. Product systems studied.

Table 2
GWP values of producing NMC batteries with 1 kWh storage capacity.

Reference	Dataset 1, kg CO ₂ -eq./ kWh	Dataset 2, kg CO ₂ -eq./ kWh	Dataset 3, kg CO ₂ -eq./ kWh
[42]	a	254	254
	b	248	254
	c	258	254
[8]	a	172	172
	b		240
	c		487
[43]	140	140	140
[9]	200	200	200
[44]	121	121	121
Mean	172	200	200
St. Dev.	± 47	± 52	± 114

[42] a – average value, whereas [42] b and c represent the values for the 25th and 75th percentiles from the probability distribution of NMC battery production,

[8] a, b, and c represent the different amount of electricity needed in the production of the NMC batteries.

3.3.2. Life cycle inventory

3.3.2.1. NMC battery manufacture. The data on the climate change impact of NMC battery production were obtained from previously published research. In the study by Ambrose and Kendall [42], the mean global warming potential (GWP), a climate change impact assessment method, of producing 1 kWh of the installed storage capacity of the NMC batteries was 254 kg CO₂-eq., whereas the values of 248 and 258 kg CO₂-eq. representing the 25th and 75th percentiles were also presented. Ellingsen et al. [8] reported a GWP of 172 kg CO₂-eq./ kWh installed capacity under the optimal production conditions, whereas values of 240 and 487 kg CO₂-eq./ kWh were reported depending on the amount of electricity consumed during the production process. Kim et al. [43] indicated a GWP value of 140 kg CO₂-eq./ kWh installed capacity. According to Majeau-Bettez et al. [9], the GWP value of producing 1 kWh of the storage capacity of NMC batteries is 200 kg CO₂-eq. Finally, in a report by the US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) [44], the GWP of manufacturing NMC batteries was 121 kg CO₂-eq./ kWh.

The five studies mentioned above published primary data on the production of NMC batteries. Table 2 lists the GWP values from the literature identified and the average GWP values, as well as their standard deviations. Based on those studies, the average GWP of producing 1 kWh of installed storage capacity in NMC batteries was calculated. The average GWP of producing 1 kWh of the storage capacity

of the NMC battery under study corresponded to 172 ± 47 kg CO₂-eq. if the average and mean values from the identified studies were used in the calculation (Dataset 1). Dataset 2 accounts for possible variation in the impact of NMC battery production resulting in a mean value of 200 ± 52 kg CO₂-eq./kWh. Dataset 3 considers a variation in the amount of electricity needed in the production of LIBs and results in the mean value of 200 ± 114 kg CO₂-eq./kWh. All in all, the value of 172 ± 47 kg CO₂-eq. per kWh storage capacity was further used in this study to present the impact of the batteries' production, as this value is based on the mean values of the sources identified and used in this study.

3.3.2.2. NMC battery use. During the use phase the batteries do not have a direct climate change impact, rather the impact occurs through potential substitution of electricity from the grid with solar electricity stored in the NMC batteries and securely delivered to the customer. The GWP values of electricity grid mixes of different countries were retrieved from the study by Moro and Lonza [45] representing the values for consumed electricity at low voltage including the impact from upstream processes, as well as from the Ecoinvent 3.5 database [46] representing low voltage electricity at the consumer. The GWP values were averaged from the two sources and the values used in this study were: Bulgaria – 0.672 ± 0.003 kg CO₂-eq./ kWh, Finland – 0.231 ± 0.020 kg CO₂-eq./ kWh, Germany – 0.613 ± 0.002 kg CO₂-eq./ kWh, Netherlands – 0.605 ± 0.036 kg CO₂-eq./ kWh, Norway – 0.021 ± 0.012 kg CO₂-eq./ kWh, and Spain – 0.349 ± 0.008 kg CO₂-eq./ kWh.

The production of electricity in the alternative scenario implied the use of solar panels. The climate change impacts from solar electricity generation using polycrystalline silicon panels installed on roofs with 3 kWp capacity were retrieved from the Ecoinvent 3.5 database [46]. Because the dataset for solar electricity generation in Norway was not available in the dataset, the dataset for Finland was also used for Norway. The datasets on solar electricity generation include the impact from solar panels production, water use for cleaning the panels, and wastewater treatment, while the impact from solar panels recycling was not included. According to Corcelli et al. [47], the cut-off impact on climate change from recycling 1 m² of monocrystalline silicon solar panels is 26.4 kg CO₂-eq. Normalising the value to 1 kWh of electricity generated in PVs using the same modelling parameters as in the datasets of Ecoinvent 3.5 resulted in an impact of 0.0063 kg CO₂-eq. This value was included in the climate change impact of solar electricity generation.

An increasing share of renewable energy sources in grid mixes was accounted for in this study. The statistics on renewable electricity output by the World Bank [48] were used to estimate the increase in the share of renewables in the future. Using historical data from the years 2000 and 2008–2015, the share of renewables in 2018, which was modelled as the year of installation of the NMC batteries and PV panels, and in 2025, which was the year when LIBs were expected to reach their end-of-life, were extrapolated using a linear function as shown in Fig. 2. The expected shares of renewables were used to model the carbon intensity of the grids in the future assuming that renewable electricity is climate-neutral. The shares of renewables calculated and used in this study in 2018 (and 2025) were as follows: Bulgaria, 17% (23%); Finland, 40% (44%); Germany, 31% (42%); Netherlands, 15% (19%); and Spain, 43% (54%). The share of renewable electricity output in Norway was constantly above 97% over the period studied. Therefore, no changes in the renewable energy output were modelled for Norway.

3.3.2.3. NMC battery recycling. There are multiple processes available for recycling NMC batteries. According to Zeng et al. [49], all LIBs recycling processes can be divided into mechanical, pyrometallurgical, hydrometallurgical, and biological. According to them [49], research on hydrometallurgical recycling of batteries occupies 58% of all

research activities in the field. During the recycling process, batteries are dismantled into different parts, and then metal-containing fractions are incinerated and slag is leached with chemicals to selectively regain metals.

Primary data on NMC batteries recycling is limited and uncertain and none of existing studies are known to go deep into different aspects of batteries recycling [50]. According to Hawkins et al. [51], recycling of LIBs with 1 kWh storage capacity has a GWP of 3.6 kg CO₂-eq. which includes dismantling and cryogenic treatment. Ellingsen et al. [7] indicated a GWP of 8 kg CO₂-eq./ kWh for recycling of NMC batteries by the pyrometallurgical process. Li et al. [52] determined the GWP of LIBs recycling to be 27 kg CO₂-eq./ kWh. Finally, a US EPA report [44] indicates a GWP value of 16–32 kg CO₂-eq./ kWh. Therefore, the median GWP value used in this study for LIBs recycling was 16 ± 11 kg CO₂-eq./ kWh. The value only represents the impact of the recycling process on the environment omitting the potential avoided impact due to the substitution of metals recovered, i.e. the so-called “cut-off” approach.

3.3.3. Life cycle impact assessment

The impact assessment was performed using the impact category of global warming (GWP 100a) with the results characterized using the impact assessment method CML2001 - August 2016.

3.3.4. Carbon handprint

Although the use phase of LIBs has no direct environmental impact, their use could result in a reduced climate change impact, due to potential customers utilizing NMC batteries together with PV panels. This reduction in climate change impact due to customers using the alternative solution, also referred to as a handprint solution, is known as the carbon handprint. Carbon handprint was calculated in this study using the methodology described by Grönman et al. [53]. Fig. 3 shows a common practice of illustrating the carbon handprint framework. The carbon handprint was calculated as the difference between the carbon footprints of the baseline and the alternative handprint solution. Carbon handprint was expressed in kilograms of carbon dioxide equivalent (kg CO₂-eq.) per functional unit of 25.3 MWh of electricity delivered to the customer in the reference case of the battery lifetime model.

3.3.5. Combination of stress factors and climate change impacts

Stress factors affect battery lifetime and thus have a high climate change impact potential. Since the batteries are used for storage of renewable energy (in this study solar electricity), the lifetime of the batteries affects their energy throughput. The battery lifetime model developed in this study was used to estimate the number of FCEs achieved with NMC batteries under various cycling conditions. The number of FCEs was then used to calculate the energy throughput of the batteries during their expected lifetime and to calculate the avoided impact achieved through consumption of renewable energy and avoided use of electricity from the grid. The estimated cycle life thus only affects the amount of electricity throughput of the batteries, while the impacts from production and disposal of the batteries remain the same.

4. Results

4.1. Stress factor models

The most comprehensive cycle life test results with varying cycle depth for NMC cells found from the literature are those of Ecker et al. [28], who have cycled commercial high energy NMC cells at 35 °C with 1C and cycle depths of 5%, 10%, 20%, 50%, 80% and 100%. The cycle life in full cycle equivalents (FCE) at 80% SOH for each cycle depth obtained from Ecker et al. [28] is presented in Fig. 4. normalized according to a cycle life with 100% cycle depth. An exponential model

Fig. 2. Share of renewable electricity output in the studied countries. Based on the data from the World Bank [48].

was fitted to the data to model the effect of cycle depth on the cycle life of NMC batteries.

The following cycle depth stress factor model was formed for NMC chemistry:

$$f_{\Delta DOD}^{cyc}(\Delta DOD) = 18.76e^{-5.1 \Delta DOD} + 0.886 \quad (5)$$

The cycle depth stress factor model covers the whole cycle depth range from 0% to 100%. However, the results of the model at the lower end of the range should be treated with caution as the experimental data by Ecker et al. [28] indicates a notably higher increase in cycle life with low cycle depths compared to other experimental results found from the literature.

Ecker et al. [28] also present extensive results on the cycle life of NMC cells cycled at different average SOC. In that study [28], the capacity fade at 750 FCE is presented for NMC cells cycled with several cycle depths and with an average SOC of 10%, 25%, 50%, 75%, 90% and 95%. From these results, the cycle life of the NMC cells at 80% SOH was calculated using linear extrapolation or interpolation when needed. The obtained results are presented in Fig. 5 normalized according to the cycle life at 50% average SOC. A two-piece Gaussian model was fitted to the data to model the effect of average SOC on the cycle life of NMC batteries.

The following average SOC stress factor model was formed for NMC chemistry:

$$f_{SOC}^{cyc}(SOC) = \begin{cases} 0.88e^{-\left(\frac{SOC-0.5}{0.3}\right)^2} + 0.12, & 0 \leq SOC \leq 0.5 \\ 0.745e^{-\left(\frac{SOC-0.5}{0.215}\right)^2} + 0.255, & 0.5 < SOC \leq 1 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Käbitz et al. [21] have cycled high energy NMC cells with 1C and 100% cycle depth at 25 °C, 40 °C and 60 °C. Richter et al. [22] have carried out corresponding cycle testing for different NMC cells at 25 °C, 32.5 °C, 42.3 °C and 55 °C. As no cycle life data set for NMC cells with cycling temperatures below room temperature were found from the literature, the NMC data sets were supplemented with NMC-LMO cell cycle life test results from Wang et al. [30], who studied the cycle life of NMC-LMO cells at 10 °C, 22 °C, 34 °C and 46 °C. These data sets were normalized according to the cycle life at room temperature (22–25 °C) and are presented in Fig. 6. The data sets from Wang et al. [30] correspond well to the data from Käbitz et al. [21] and Richter et al. [22] at

temperatures above room temperature. A Gaussian model was fitted to the data to model the effect of temperature on the cycle life of NMC batteries.

The following temperature stress factor model was formed for NMC chemistry:

$$f_T^{cyc}(T) = e^{-\left(\frac{T-23.22}{20.61}\right)^2} \quad (7)$$

The measurement data supports the temperature stress factor model well between 20 °C and 50 °C, whereas the accuracy at lower temperatures suffers from lack of measurement points.

4.2. Cycle life model

The previously formed stress factor models were combined in a cycle life model that estimates the cycle life of the battery in different temperatures and cycling conditions. Results from the cycle life model developed for the NMC cells are presented in Fig. 7.

The most relevant results with respect to the application were selected to be included in the LCA calculations to be able to compare the effect of different stress factor conditions on the environmental impact of the battery (Section 4.6). The estimated cycle life for the investigated NMC battery under selected stress factor conditions is presented in Table 3.

4.3. Carbon footprint of the baseline scenario

Fig. 8 shows the results of the cumulative carbon footprint of electricity production using the grid mix technologies during 7.7 years, which was the expected lifetime of the NMC batteries studied under the reference cycling conditions. The results are presented for the six countries studied. The results are expressed per total electricity throughput of the studied battery during its lifetime – 25.3 MWh. The impact of capital goods needed to generate and distribute electricity is included in the carbon footprint of electricity and thus is not displayed separately in the figure. The error bars in the carbon footprint of the electricity from the grid represent the variation in the carbon intensity identified between the two data sources included, as well as the expected increase in the share of renewable electricity in the future as described in Section 3.3.2. The impact from the disposal of

* - the disposal of existing infrastructure to deliver electricity in the grids is excluded since the grids are not meant for demolishing within foreseen timeframe,
 [1] – datasets for country-specific markets for electricity at low voltage from the Ecoinvent 3.5 database,
 [2] – A. Moro, L. Lonza, Electricity carbon intensity in European Member States: Impacts on GHG emissions of electric vehicles, Transp. Res. Part D Transp. Environ. (2017).

Fig. 3. Carbon handprint framework used for the assessment of the carbon handprint.

Fig. 4. Cycle depth stress factor model based on the data of Ecker et al. [28].

Fig. 5. Average SOC stress factor model based on the data of Ecker et al. [28].

Fig. 6. Temperature stress factor model based on the data of [21,22,30].

infrastructure required to deliver electricity from the grid is not included due to the anticipated use of this infrastructure in the future even after implementation of the alternative solution. The carbon footprint of the baseline solution was calculated following Eq. (8).

$$CF_{average, 2025}^{baseline} = CF_{initiation} + \frac{1}{n} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n CI_{grid} \cdot E \quad (8)$$

where $CF_{initiation}$ is the carbon footprint of constructing the grid. In this calculation, the impact is considered as a part of the electricity provision CI_{grid} .

CI_{grid} is the carbon intensity of electricity grid mix calculated as an average of two studies ($n = 2$), and E is the electrical energy throughput during the expected service life of the NMC battery of 7.7 years (25.3 MWh under the reference cycling conditions).

The carbon intensity of the electricity in the year 2025 was adjusted to account for the increasing share of renewables, which is considered in the negative error bar.

The cumulative carbon footprint in the studied countries is (in descending order): 17,000 kg CO₂-eq. in Bulgaria; 15,500 kg CO₂-eq. in Germany; 15,300 kg CO₂-eq. in the Netherlands; 8800 kg CO₂-eq. in Spain; 5800 kg CO₂-eq. in Finland; and 520 kg CO₂-eq. in Norway. The carbon intensity of electricity from the grid is related to the types of fuels used, which are shown in Fig. 9. As can be seen, coal dominates electricity generation in the countries with the highest carbon intensities, which were Bulgaria, Germany, and the Netherlands, and represented 39–46% of the total electricity output in 2015. In contrast, Finland produces 75% of its electricity from biofuels, hydropower and nuclear energy, and thus has a moderately low carbon intensity electricity grid. The lowest carbon intensity is attributed to Norway, which generates 96% of its electricity from hydropower.

4.4. Carbon footprint of the alternative solution

The impact from the alternative, handprint, solution is shown in Fig. 10. The impact begins with the production of one NMC battery with a storage capacity of 10 kWh, which had an impact of 1720 kg CO₂-eq. The error bar for the impact from NMC battery production represents the variation in the available data. As can be seen, the variation of 47 kg CO₂-eq. per kWh of installed storage capacity identified in this study represents a considerable uncertainty compared to the cumulative impact of the alternative solution: 11–13% of the cumulative impact of the handprint solution depending on the country. Therefore, the data on the impacts of the production of NMC batteries should be assessed more critically in attributional assessments of PV-battery systems. The cumulative impact of the alternative solution is (in descending order): 4250 kg CO₂-eq. in Germany; 4200 kg CO₂-eq. in the Netherlands; 3800 kg CO₂-eq. in Finland and Norway; 3550 kg CO₂-eq. in Bulgaria; and 3400 kg CO₂-eq. in Spain. The lower impact in Southern Europe is related to higher solar irradiation and thus higher availability of solar panels. The carbon footprint of the alternative, handprint, solution was calculated following Eq. (9).

$$CF_{2025}^{alternative} = CF_{initiation} + CI_{solar} \cdot E \quad (9)$$

where $CF_{initiation}$ is the carbon intensity of manufacturing NMC batteries. The impact of producing PV panels is considered as a part of the electricity provision CI_{solar} .

CI_{solar} is the carbon intensity of solar electricity provision, including the impacts from producing the PV panels, and

E is the electrical energy throughput during the expected life cycle of the NMC batteries of 7.7 years (25.3 MWh under the reference cycling conditions).

4.5. Carbon handprint

Fig. 11 plots the results of the carbon handprint of the alternative solution allowing for generation of solar electricity and its storage in an NMC battery to enable secure electricity supply and avoided consumption of electricity from the grid. The carbon handprint is represented as the difference between the impact of the baseline scenario “Electricity from grid” and the alternative scenario “Solar electricity”.

Fig. 7. The cycle life model. (a) Estimated cycle life with different temperatures and average SOC when cycle depth is 50%. (b) Estimated cycle life with different cycle depths and average SOC when the temperature is 25 °C. Unrealistic cycle depth - average SOC combinations are excluded. The reference cycle life in both cases is 2810 FCE ($\Delta DOD = 90\%$, $SOC_{avg} = 50\%$, $T = 25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$).

Table 3

Results of the cycle life model in different stress factor conditions. Estimated cycle life of the battery is expressed in full cycle equivalents (FCE). Reference cycle life is marked with (*) and the results used in the LCA calculations in bolded.

15 °C						25 °C							
		Average SOC							Average SOC				
		30%	40%	50%	60%	70%			30%	40%	50%	60%	70%
ΔDOD	30%	7595	10070	11100	9491	6311	ΔDOD	30%	8838	11720	12920	11040	7344
	50%	3608	4785	5273	4509	2998		50%	4199	5569	6137	5247	3489
	70%	-	2879	3172	2713	-		70%	-	3350	3692	3157	-
	90%	-	-	2415	-	-		90%	-	-	2810*	-	-
35 °C						45 °C							
		Average SOC							Average SOC				
		30%	40%	50%	60%	70%			30%	40%	50%	60%	70%
ΔDOD	30%	6423	8518	9387	8026	5337	ΔDOD	30%	2915	3866	4260	3642	2422
	50%	3051	4047	4459	3813	2536		50%	1385	1836	2024	1730	1151
	70%	-	2434	2683	2294	-		70%	-	1105	1217	1041	-
	90%	-	-	2042	-	-		90%	-	-	927	-	-

Fig. 8. Carbon footprint of the baseline solution, i.e. electricity provision from the grid.

Table 4 summarizes the carbon handprints of the alternative solutions. The largest potential reduction in climate change impacts is identified for Bulgaria at 13,450 kg CO₂-eq. followed by Germany at 11,250 kg CO₂-eq. and the Netherlands at 11,100 kg CO₂-eq. No carbon handprint was achieved as the carbon footprint of the baseline solution was lower than that of the alternative solution. Normalizing the results to 1 kWh the carbon handprint is: 0.53 kg CO₂-eq. for Bulgaria; 0.44 kg CO₂-eq. for Germany and the Netherlands; 0.21 kg CO₂-eq. for Spain;

and 0.079 kg CO₂-eq. for Finland.

Further analysis of the results presented in Fig. 11 indicated that the alternative solution becomes more climate-friendly compared to the baseline solution within different timeframes in different countries. Under the Bulgarian, Dutch, and German conditions, the climate change impact of the alternative solution is lower than that of the baseline within the first year of operation. For Spain, the break-even point is reached during the second year of operation. Finally, the lower

Fig. 9. Shares of electricity generation by fuel in 2015 [54].

Fig. 10. Carbon footprint of the alternative solution, i.e. electricity provision from solar panels stored in a LIB.

carbon footprint of the Finnish grid mix extends the timeframe for reaching the break-even point to the fourth year of operation.

4.6. Combination of cycle life model with carbon handprint

The climate change impact of prolonged or shortened lifetime of the studied NMC batteries due to the impact of stress factors is shown in Fig. 12. The figure illustrates how service life duration affects the environmental impact of the NMC batteries during their use phase under Spanish operating conditions. For all other county-specific cases, the pattern of the impact of stress factors on battery lifetime remains the same. In total, 10 combinations of stress factors were studied in addition to the reference situation. The effect of each stress factor (cell temperature, cycle depth, and average SOC) was studied separately while keeping the other two factors constant. Battery service life was estimated at four temperatures (T): 15 °C (Case 1), 25 °C (reference),

35 °C (Case 2) and 45 °C (Case 3) while keeping the average SOC and cycle depth at the reference values. The impact of cycle depth (Δ DOD) was studied at four cycle depths: 90% (reference), 70% (Case 4), 50% (Case 5) and 30% (Case 6) while keeping the other two parameters constant. The impact of average SOC (SOC_{avg}) was studied within the range of 30–70% with a 10% increment (Cases 7–10) while keeping the other two parameters constant. The results were ranked according to the duration of the service life of the NMC battery as shown in Table 5.

The results show that a change in operating temperature from the reference 25 °C resulted in reduced battery lifetime. The temperature change is expected to reduce the service life of the NMC battery from 7.7 years to 2.5 years if the battery is used at 45 °C; to 5.6 years if the battery is used at 35 °C; and to 6.6 years if the battery is used at 15 °C. These reductions in service life led to corresponding reductions in carbon handprint, from 5400 kg CO₂-eq. to 520–4370 kg CO₂-eq. depending on the operating temperature. Decreasing the cycle depth from

Fig. 11. Carbon handprint of the alternative handprint solution of electricity provision using solar panels and its storage in an NMC battery compared with the baseline solution of electricity provision from the grid. Results are expressed per 25.3 MWh of electricity delivered, which is the amount of electricity that the studied battery can deliver during its lifetime.

Table 4
Carbon footprints of the baseline and alternative solutions, carbon handprint of the alternative solution.

Country	Carbon footprint of baseline solution		Carbon footprint of alternative solution		Carbon handprint of alternative solution	
	kg CO ₂ -eq./ 25.3 MWh	kg CO ₂ -eq./ 1 kWh	kg CO ₂ -eq./ 25.3 MWh	kg CO ₂ -eq./ 1 kWh	kg CO ₂ -eq./ 25.3 MWh	kg CO ₂ -eq./ 1 kWh
Bulgaria	17,000	0.67	3550	0.14	13,450	0.53
Germany	15,500	0.61	4250	0.17	11,250	0.44
Netherlands	15,300	0.61	4200	0.17	11,100	0.44
Spain	8800	0.35	3400	0.13	5400	0.21
Finland	5800	0.23	3800	0.15	2000	0.079
Norway	520	0.021	3800	0.15	-*	-*

* No handprint is achieved in Norway as the carbon footprint of the alternative solution is higher than the baseline solution.

the reference condition ($\Delta DOD = 90\%$) resulted in a significantly prolonged lifetime of the NMC battery. At 50% cycle depth the estimated service life of the battery would be 17 years, which is over two times the reference service life of 7.7 years achieved at 90% cycle depth. In terms of the carbon handprint this equates to an increase from 5400 kg CO₂-eq. to 14,000 kg CO₂-eq. According to the model up to 12,920 FCEs or 35 years of operation could be achieved if the cycle depth was reduced to 30%, and extending the service life to 35 years would increase the handprint from 5400 kg CO₂-eq. to 31,600 kg CO₂-eq. However, the estimated lifetime is so long that the calendar ageing processes in the battery would prevail over cycle ageing, thus increasing the uncertainty of the results. Increasing or decreasing the average SOC from 50% shortens the expected service life of the battery, though the change is not as fast as with the cycle depth. When examining the results, it should be noted that the impact of average SOC is studied at 50% cycle depth, which prolongs the estimated service life compared to the reference condition ($\Delta DOD = 90\%$). The results for all of the countries studied (excluding Norway, for which no handprint was achieved) are presented in Table 6.

Fig. 12. Impact of stress factors (cell temperature, cycle depth, and average SOC) on the service life duration of NMC batteries in Spanish operating conditions. The stress factor value shown for each non-reference case is the variable stress factor; the other two factors were kept constant.

Table 5

Stress factor values, number of FCE, energy throughput, service and termination years, and carbon handprint of the various cases assessed in Spanish operating conditions. Ranked by expected lifetime.

Case	Variable	Constant 1	Constant 2	Number of FCE	Energy throughput (E), MWh	Expected lifetime, years	Termination year	Carbon handprint, kg CO ₂ -eq.
3	T 45 °C	SOC 50%	ΔDOD 90%	927	8.3	2.5	2020	520
2	T 35 °C	SOC 50%	ΔDOD 90%	2042	18	5.6	2023	3410
1	T 15 °C	SOC 50%	ΔDOD 90%	2415	22	6.6	2024	4370
Ref.	ΔDOD 90%	SOC 50%	T 25 °C	2810	25	7.7	2025	5400
10	SOC 70%	ΔDOD 50%	T 25 °C	3489	31	9.6	2027	7150
4	ΔDOD 70%	SOC 50%	T 25 °C	3692	33	10	2028	7680
7	SOC 30%	ΔDOD 50%	T 25 °C	4199	38	12	2029	8990
9	SOC 60%	ΔDOD 50%	T 25 °C	5247	47	14	2032	11,700
8	SOC 40%	ΔDOD 50%	T 25 °C	5569	50	15	2033	12,500
5	ΔDOD 50%	SOC 50%	T 25 °C	6137	55	17	2034	14,000
6	ΔDOD 30%	SOC 50%	T 25 °C	12,920	120	35	2053	31,600

Table 6

Carbon handprints of the different cases based on the impact of stress factors on battery lifetime per country.

Case	Energy throughput (E), MWh	Expected lifetime, years	Carbon handprint, kg CO ₂ -eq.				
			Spain	Bulgaria	Germany	The Netherlands	Finland
3	8.3	2.5	520	3180	2460	2400	-579
2	18	5.6	3410	9260	7660	7560	990
1	22	6.6	4370	11,300	9400	9280	1510
Ref.	25	7.7	5400	13,450	11,250	11,100	2000
10	31	10	7150	17,200	14,400	14,200	3000
4	33	10	7680	18,300	15,400	15,200	3300
7	38	12	8990	21,000	17,700	17,500	4000
9	47	14	11,700	26,800	22,700	22,400	5500
8	50	15	12,500	28,500	24,100	23,800	5900
5	55	17	14,000	31,600	26,800	26,500	6700
6	120	35	31,600	68,600	58,500	57,800	16,300

Fig. 13 shows that climate change impact reduction gradually increases in line with prolonged battery lifetime. The reduction was calculated as the relative difference between the impact of the baseline solution and the alternative solution in relation to the impact of the baseline solution for each case, including the reference, accounting for the varying energy throughput (E) (Table 5) under various conditions. The relative impact of NMC battery production and recycling diminishes significantly with increased battery service life. As can be seen after 5–10 years of operation, the relative reduction in climate change impact starts to level out as the impact from battery production and recycling per each kWh of electricity replaced becomes minor. The reduction in climate change impacts was calculated using Eq. (10).

$$CF_{Reduction} = \frac{CF_{average, j}^{baseline} - CF_j^{alternative}}{CF_j^{alternative}} \quad (10)$$

where $CF_{average, j}^{baseline}$ is the carbon footprint of the baseline solution in case j accounting for the corresponding energy throughput (Table 6), and

$CF_j^{alternative}$ is the carbon footprint of the alternative solution in case j accounting for the same energy throughput as in the baseline solution.

5. Discussion

The use of batteries, such as Li-ion batteries, is known to be one of the most effective ways of increasing household self-consumption of

Fig. 13. Reduction in climate change impact with the studied alternative scenario compared to the baseline.

photovoltaic electricity [55]. Coupling photovoltaics electricity generation system with batteries enables efficient utilization of surplus electricity generated during daytime [56]. At the same time, load shifting in the grid is maintained, thus reducing the risks of power distribution failure. Another study [57] has shown that NMC batteries coupled with PV panels could significantly reduce the impact on climate change when compared with the default scenario of utilizing electricity from grid. However, other solutions, such as flow batteries, fuels cells, and NiMH batteries among others, can be applied for distributed energy storage [58]. Therefore, the impact of alternative solutions should also be quantified and compared to identify the solution with the largest carbon handprint potential.

Li-ion batteries are among the most commonly used battery types for small devices and there is a growing interest in their use in larger applications due to their high efficiency, reliability, and high energy density [58]. However, their high cost still hinders their use in wider applications. The environmental impact of producing NMC and lithium iron phosphate (LFP) batteries has been studied more intensively than other LIB chemistries [4], accounting for the higher availability and robustness of data on these battery chemistries. According to one study [5], LFP batteries have consistently lower impact across several impact categories compared to NMC batteries. This would imply that the production phase impacts could be further reduced by using LFP batteries instead of NMC; however, LFP batteries generally have lower specific energy.

This study focused solely on climate change impacts and on quantifying the potential benefits of employing alternative systems of electricity generation for mitigating climate change. This focus was chosen as climate change mitigation is the key driver for the deployment of renewable energy sources and should be used as an indicator of the feasibility of such solutions. This could, however, be a significant limitation as the production and recycling of batteries are expected to have considerable abiotic resource depletion and toxicity-related impacts. One study [51] indicates that human toxicity potential could be a key challenge when shifting towards systems deploying LIBs. The toxic impact originates predominantly from the disposal of sulfidic mine tailings generated during mining of copper, nickel, and other metals. However, human toxicity related impacts embody comparatively higher uncertainty in the impact assessment phase compared to GWP [59] and thus should be applied with caution. Furthermore, the recycling of batteries increases the uncertainty regarding their toxic impacts.

The situation assessed in this study involving the use of a PV battery system is hypothetical, representing one of the potential scenarios for increased use of renewable energy in households. The calculated potential reduction in climate change impacts in this study only indicates

the direction of future development under the assumptions of this study. The calculated handprint values may vary depending on the actual behaviour of users, which might affect the intensity of the batteries use, their operating conditions, cycle depth and other parameters, which significantly affect their service life and the amount of electricity replaced. However, the results indicated that the impact of the production and recycling of NMC batteries diminishes as the service life extends under the most optimal operating conditions.

As the cycle life model developed in this study is based on experimental data, its accuracy is dependent on the availability of comprehensive experimental results. Finding sufficient and comprehensive experimental results from the literature is challenging, especially since the effect of the stress factors on battery lifetime varies even between different Li-ion battery chemistries. Ecker et al. [28] present comprehensive experimental results for different cycle depths and average SOCs, yet other comparable data sets would be needed to increase the reliability of the cycle depth and average SOC stress factor models. Temperatures above room temperature are relatively well represented in the data sets available, but the lack of experimental results at lower temperatures weakens the usability of the model in such operating conditions.

The lifetime model in this study focuses on modelling the effect of cycle ageing stress factors on the cycle life of the battery. The lifetime of the battery in different conditions was estimated based on the stress factor models and the reference lifetime. The reference lifetime contains the impact of calendar ageing in the reference conditions, but the more the result of the model differs from the reference lifetime, the greater the possible error in the lifetime estimation. Therefore more comprehensive consideration of calendar ageing in the lifetime model would increase the accuracy of the model and thus should be taken into account in the future development of the model.

6. Conclusions

Comparison of a hypothetical future scenario of increasing use of photovoltaics in households and storage of intermittent electricity in Li-ion batteries to avoid consumption of electricity from the grid showed significant potential for reducing climate change impacts and thus creating a carbon handprint for potential solution providers. Of the six countries studied, the largest reductions of 13,450 kg CO₂-eq., 11,250 kg CO₂-eq., and 11,100 kg CO₂-eq. per 25.3 MWh, which was the energy throughput of the studied battery during its lifetime, could be achieved in Bulgaria, Germany, and the Netherlands, respectively. The high potential reduction is due to the high carbon intensity of the electricity grid in those countries associated with the use of coal, where coal accounts for ca. 40–45% of electricity output. In contrast, there are

no potential benefits for Norwegian households, as the impact from producing, using, and disposing of batteries and solar panels significantly outweighs the impact of producing electricity from hydropower, which accounts for 96% of the current Norwegian electricity output.

Uncertainty related to the impact from producing and disposing of the batteries becomes less prominent when a comparison is done with the existing grid mix, although this uncertainty would be important when performing attributional impact assessment of PV battery systems. The reduction in climate change impacts compared with the baseline scenario increases gradually in line with the increasing service life of the batteries due to the decreasing relative impact of battery production and disposal. The analysis of the battery cycle life model showed that the expected number of cycles can range dramatically under different conditions. It was shown that a change in operating temperature from the reference value of 25 °C to 15 °C or 45 °C results in a corresponding reduction in the number of battery cycles from 2810 cycles to 2420 and 930 cycles, respectively, which in turn will reduce the carbon handprint of the provided solution. In contrast, shallow cycles substantially prolong the service life of the battery. Decreasing the cycle depth from 90% to 50% increased the number of cycles from 2810 full cycle equivalents to 6137 full cycle equivalents, which more than doubles the carbon handprint in all the counties studied except Norway.

Declaration of Competing Interest

None.

Acknowledgments

This work has been supported by the INVADE H2020 project (2017–2019), which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement no. 731148.

References

- IRENA, Accelerating renewables is our most effective climate solution, (2018).
- N.S. Lewis, Research opportunities to advance solar energy utilization, *Science* 80 (351) (2016), <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aad1920>.
- N. Opiyo, Energy storage systems for PV-based communal grids, *J. Energy Storage* 7 (2016) 1–12, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2016.05.001>.
- B. Zimmermann, J. Braun, M. Baumann, M. Weil, J.F. Peters, The environmental impact of Li-Ion batteries and the role of key parameters – a review, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 67 (2016) 491–506, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.08.039>.
- J.F. Peters, M. Weil, Providing a common base for life cycle assessments of Li-Ion batteries, *J. Clean. Prod.* 171 (2018) 704–713, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.10.016>.
- L.A.W. Ellingsen, C.R. Hung, A.H. Strømman, Identifying key assumptions and differences in life cycle assessment studies of lithium-ion traction batteries with focus on greenhouse gas emissions, *Transp. Res. Part D Transp. Environ.* 55 (2017) 82–90, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2017.06.028>.
- L.A.-W. Ellingsen, B. Singh, A.H. Strømman, The size and range effect: lifecycle greenhouse gas emissions of electric vehicles, *Environ. Res. Lett.* 11 (2016) 054010, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/11/5/054010>.
- L.A.-W. Ellingsen, G. Majeau-Bettez, B. Singh, A.K. Srivastava, L.O. Valøen, A.H. Strømman, Life cycle assessment of a lithium-ion battery vehicle pack, *J. Ind. Ecol.* 18 (2014) 113–124, <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.12072>.
- G. Majeau-Bettez, T.R. Hawkins, A.H. Strømman, Life cycle environmental assessment of lithium-ion and nickel metal hydride batteries for plug-in hybrid and battery electric vehicles, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 45 (2011) 4548–4554, <https://doi.org/10.1021/es103607c>.
- A. Barré, B. Deguilhem, S. Grolleau, M. Gérard, F. Suard, D. Riu, A review on lithium-ion battery ageing mechanisms and estimations for automotive applications, *J. Power Sources* 241 (2013) 680–689, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2013.05.040>.
- S.M. Rezvanianani, Z. Liu, Y. Chen, J. Lee, Review and recent advances in battery health monitoring and prognostics technologies for electric vehicle (EV) safety and mobility, *J. Power Sources* 256 (2014) 110–124, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2014.01.085>.
- M. Jafari, K. Khan, L. Gauchia, Deterministic models of Li-ion battery aging: It is a matter of scale, *J. Energy Storage* 20 (2018) 67–77, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2018.09.002>.
- C. Pillot, Lithium-ion battery raw material supply and demand 2017–2025, *Adv. Automot. Batter. Conf.* 2018.
- I. Tsiropoulos, D. Tarvydas, N. Lebedeva, Li-ion batteries for mobility and stationary storage applications – scenarios for costs and market growth, 2018. doi:10.2760/87175.
- J. Vetter, P. Novák, M.R. Wagner, C. Veit, K.C. Möller, J.O. Besenhard, M. Winter, M. Wohlfahrt-Mehrens, C. Vogler, A. Hammouche, Ageing mechanisms in lithium-ion batteries, *J. Power Sources* 147 (2005) 269–281, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2005.01.006>.
- C.R. Birkl, M.R. Roberts, E. Mcturk, P.G. Bruce, D.A. Howey, Degradation diagnostics for lithium ion cells, *J. Power Sources* 341 (2017) 373–386 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2016.12.011>.
- H. Wenzl, I. Baring-Gould, R. Kaiser, B.Y. Liaw, P. Lundsager, J. Manwell, A. Ruddell, V. Svoboda, Life prediction of batteries for selecting the technically most suitable and cost effective battery, *J. Power Sources* 144 (2005) 373–384, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2004.11.045>.
- B. Xu, A. Oudalov, A. Ulbig, G. Andersson, D.S. Kirschen, Modeling of lithium-ion battery degradation for cell life assessment modeling of lithium-ion battery degradation for cell life assessment, *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid* 9 (2016) 1131–1140, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSG.2016.2578950>.
- A. Cordoba-Arenas, S. Onori, Y. Guezennec, G. Rizzoni, Capacity and power fade cycle-life model for plug-in hybrid electric vehicle lithium-ion battery cells containing blended spinel and layered-oxide positive electrodes, *J. Power Sources* 278 (2015) 473–483, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2014.12.047>.
- J. Schmalstieg, S. Käbitz, M. Ecker, D.U. Sauer, A holistic aging model for Li (NiMnCo)O₂ based 18650 lithium-ion batteries, *J. Power Sources* 257 (2014) 325–334, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2014.02.012>.
- S. Käbitz, J.B. Gerschler, M. Ecker, Y. Yurdagel, B. Emmermacher, D. André, T. Mitsch, D.U. Sauer, Cycle and calendar life study of a graphite/LiNi₁/3Mn 1/3Co₁/3O₂ Li-ion high energy system. Part A: full cell characterization, *J. Power Sources* 239 (2013) 572–583, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2013.03.045>.
- F. Richter, P.J.S. Vie, S. Kjelstrup, O.S. Burheim, Measurements of ageing and thermal conductivity in a secondary NMC-hard carbon Li-ion battery and the impact on internal temperature profiles, *Electrochim. Acta* 250 (2017) 228–237, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2017.07.173>.
- J. Schmitt, A. Maheshwari, M. Heck, S. Lux, M. Vetter, Impedance change and capacity fade of lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide-based batteries during calendar aging, *J. Power Sources* 353 (2017) 183–194, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2017.03.090>.
- S. Wu, P.H. Lee, Storage fading of a commercial 18650 cell comprised with NMC/LMO cathode and graphite anode, *J. Power Sources* 349 (2017) 27–36, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2017.03.002>.
- S. Grolleau, A. Delaille, H. Gualous, P. Gyan, R. Revel, J. Bernard, E. Redondo-Iglesias, J. Peter, Calendar aging of commercial graphite/LiFePO₄cell – predicting capacity fade under time dependent storage conditions, *J. Power Sources* 255 (2014) 450–458, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2013.11.098>.
- M. Lewerenz, J. Münnix, J. Schmalstieg, S. Käbitz, M. Knips, D.U. Sauer, Systematic aging of commercial LiFePO₄/Graphite cylindrical cells including a theory explaining rise of capacity during aging, *J. Power Sources* 345 (2017) 254–263, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2017.01.133>.
- E. Redondo-Iglesias, P. Venet, S. Pelissier, Eyring acceleration model for predicting calendar ageing of lithium-ion batteries, *J. Energy Storage* 13 (2017) 176–183, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2017.06.009>.
- M. Ecker, N. Nieto, S. Käbitz, J. Schmalstieg, H. Blanke, A. Warnecke, D.U. Sauer, Calendar and cycle life study of Li(NiMnCo)O₂-based 18650 lithium-ion batteries, *J. Power Sources* 248 (2014) 839–851, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2013.09.143>.
- J. de Hoog, J.M. Timmermans, D. Ioan-Stroe, M. Swierczynski, J. Jaguemont, S. Goutam, N. Omar, J. Van Mierlo, P. Van Den Bossche, Combined cycling and calendar capacity fade modeling of a Nickel-Manganese-Cobalt Oxide Cell with real-life profile validation, *Appl. Energy* 200 (2017) 47–61, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.05.018>.
- J. Wang, J. Purewal, P. Liu, J. Hicks-Garner, S. Soukiazian, E. Sherman, A. Sorenson, L. Vu, H.-G. J. S. S. H. Tataria, M.W. Verbrugge, V. L. T. H. V. MW, Degradation of lithium ion batteries employing graphite negatives and nickel-cobalt-manganese oxide plus spinel manganese oxide positives: part 1, aging mechanisms and life estimation, *J. Power Sources* 269 (2014) 937–948.
- N. Omar, M.A. Monem, Y. Firouz, J. Salminen, J. Smekens, O. Hegazy, H. Gualous, G. Mulder, P. Van den Bossche, T. Coosemans, J. Van Mierlo, Lithium iron phosphate based battery – assessment of the aging parameters and development of cycle life model, *Appl. Energy* 113 (2014) 1575–1585, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2013.09.003>.
- I.V. E. Sarasketa-Zabala, I. Gandiaga, E. Martinez-Laserna, L.M. Rodriguez-Martinez, Cycle ageing analysis of a LiFePO₄/graphite cell with dynamic model validations: towards realistic lifetime predictions, 275 (2015) 573–587.
- J. Jiang, W. Shi, J. Zheng, P. Zuo, J. Xiao, X. Chen, W. Xu, J.-G. Zhang, Optimized operating range for large-format LiFePO₄/graphite batteries, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 161 (2013) A336–A341, <https://doi.org/10.1149/2.052403jes>.
- M. Petzl, M.A. Danzer, Nondestructive detection, characterization, and quantification of lithium plating in commercial lithium-ion batteries, *J. Power Sources* 254 (2014) 80–87, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2013.12.060>.
- K. Jalkanen, J. Karppinen, L. Skogström, T. Laurila, M. Nisula, K. Vuorilehto, Cycle aging of commercial NMC/graphite pouch cells at different temperatures, *Appl. Energy* 154 (2015) 160–172, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2015.04.110>.
- L. Tan, L. Zhang, Q. Sun, M. Shen, Q. Qu, H. Zheng, Capacity loss induced by lithium deposition at graphite anode for LiFePO₄/graphite cell cycling at different

- temperatures, *Electrochim. Acta* 111 (2013) 802–808, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2013.08.074>.
- [37] S.F. Schuster, T. Bach, E. Fleder, J. Müller, M. Brand, G. Sextl, A. Jossen, Nonlinear aging characteristics of lithium-ion cells under different operational conditions, *J. Energy Storage* 1 (2015) 44–53, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2015.05.003>.
- [38] P. Keil, A. Jossen, Charging protocols for lithium-ion batteries and their impact on cycle life-an experimental study with different 18650 high-power cells, *J. Energy Storage* 6 (2016) 125–141, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2016.02.005>.
- [39] B. Xu, A. Oudalov, A. Ulbig, G. Andersson, D.S. Kirschen, Modeling of lithium-ion battery degradation for cell life assessment modeling of lithium-ion battery degradation for cell life assessment, *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid* 9 (2018) 1131–1140, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSG.2016.2578950>.
- [40] SFS-EN ISO 14040, Environmental management – life cycle assessment – principles and framework (ISO 14040:2006), 2006.
- [41] SFS-EN ISO 14044, Environmental management – life cycle assessment – requirements and guidelines (ISO 14044:2006), 2006.
- [42] H. Ambrose, A. Kendall, Effects of battery chemistry and performance on the life cycle greenhouse gas intensity of electric mobility, *Transp. Res. Part D Transp. Environ.* 47 (2016) 182–194, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2016.05.009>.
- [43] H.C. Kim, T.J. Wallington, R. Arsenault, C. Bae, S. Ahn, J. Lee, Cradle-to-gate emissions from a commercial electric vehicle li-ion battery: a comparative analysis, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 50 (2016) 7715–7722, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.6b00830>.
- [44] U.S. EPA, Application of life-cycle assessment to nanoscale technology: lithium-ion batteries for electric vehicles, 2013. doi:10.1038/nchem.2085.
- [45] A. Moro, L. Lonza, Electricity carbon intensity in European Member States: Impacts on GHG emissions of electric vehicles, *Transp. Res. Part D Transp. Environ.* (2017), <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TRD.2017.07.012>.
- [46] G. Wernet, C. Bauer, B. Steubing, J. Reinhard, E. Moreno-Ruiz, B. Weidema, The ecoinvent database version 3 (part I): overview and methodology, *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 21 (2016) 1218–1230, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-016-1087-8>.
- [47] F. Corcelli, M. Tammaro, S. Ulgiati, L. Sannino, M. Ripa, E. Leccisi, G. Graditi, V. Fiandra, V. Cigolotti, Sustainable urban electricity supply chain – indicators of material recovery and energy savings from crystalline silicon photovoltaic panels end-of-life, *Ecol. Indic.* 94 (2016) 37–51, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2016.03.028>.
- [48] World Bank, Renewable electricity output (% of total electricity output), (2018).
- [49] X. Zeng, J. Li, N. Singh, Recycling of spent lithium-ion battery: a critical review, *Crit. Rev. Environ. Sci. Technol.* 44 (2014) 1129–1165, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10643389.2013.763578>.
- [50] H.E. Melin, State-of-the-art in reuse and recycling of lithium-ion batteries – a research review, 2019.
- [51] T.R. Hawkins, B. Singh, G. Majeau-Bettez, A.H. Strømman, Comparative environmental life cycle assessment of conventional and electric vehicles, *J. Ind. Ecol.* 17 (2013) 53–64, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1530-9290.2012.00532.x>.
- [52] B. Li, X. Gao, J. Li, C. Yuan, Life cycle environmental impact of high-capacity lithium ion battery with silicon nanowires anode for electric vehicles, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 48 (2014) 3047–3055, <https://doi.org/10.1021/es4037786>.
- [53] M. Leino, R. Soukka, A. Soininen, S. Vatanen, K. Grönman, J. Sillman, T. Pajula, H. Kasurinen, Carbon handprint – an approach to assess the positive climate impacts of products demonstrated via renewable diesel case, *J. Clean. Prod.* 206 (2018) 1059–1072, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.09.233>.
- [54] IEA, Electricity information, (2018).
- [55] R. Luthander, J. Widén, D. Nilsson, J. Palm, Photovoltaic self-consumption in buildings: a review, *Appl. Energy* 142 (2015) 80–94, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2014.12.028>.
- [56] L. Barelli, G. Bidini, F. Bonucci, A micro-grid operation analysis for cost-effective battery energy storage and RES plants integration, *Energy* 113 (2016) 831–844, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2016.07.117>.
- [57] A. Bilich, K. Langham, R. Geyer, L. Goyal, J. Hansen, A. Krishnan, J. Bergesen, P. Sinha, Life cycle assessment of solar photovoltaic microgrid systems in off-grid communities, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 51 (2017) 1043–1052, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.6b05455>.
- [58] H.L. Ferreira, R. Garde, G. Fulli, W. Kling, J.P. Lopes, Characterisation of electrical energy storage technologies, *Energy* 53 (2013) 288–298, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2013.02.037>.
- [59] M.Z. Hauschild, M. Goedkoop, J. Guinée, R. Heijungs, M. Huijbregts, O. Jolliet, M. Margni, A. De Schryver, S. Humbert, A. Laurent, S. Sala, R. Pant, Identifying best existing practice for characterization modeling in life cycle impact assessment, *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 18 (2013) 683–697, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-012-0489-5>.